

WORKING TOGETHER FOR A SHARED PAST AND A GREENER FUTURE

Contents

—

4

Taken at the Flood

5

Archaeology of the Continental Shelf

7

Marine Development and Archaeology

10

Work To Date and Looking Towards The Future

Taken at the FLOOD

Offshore windfarms will expand significantly over the next decades as nations adopt clean-energy strategies. Such initiatives are a welcome response to climate change, and the UK aims to power all homes using offshore wind by 2030. The scale and rapidity of this development is unprecedented. The need for developers to work with stakeholders to protect the marine environment has never been greater. The preservation and protection of marine heritage is an important aspect of development, and many may not realise the impact of proposed developments, particularly upon prehistoric Underwater Cultural Heritage in areas such as the southern North Sea, which contains Europe's largest and best-preserved prehistoric landscape, "Doggerland".

Over the last twenty years, European research has begun to reveal a vast prehistoric landscape beneath the North Sea, lost to sea level rise after the last Ice Age. Technological developments mean we can now trace its shorelines, rivers, lakes and valleys. Similar landscapes exist on other continental shelves, but Doggerland is the most extensively studied of anywhere in the world. However, significant gaps remain in our knowledge. Whilst we know much about the physical landscape of Doggerland, no evidence of settlement or 'in situ' activity, that is, archaeology in its original location, is known from the offshore zone of the North Sea, beyond the limit of Territorial waters. Our understanding of the communities who lived there is little better than it was over a century ago. Ultimately, the most significant staging ground for the last hunter-gatherers of Northwest Europe remains archaeological "terra incognita".

Many countries around the North Sea are beginning to appreciate the importance of this area and providing curatorial protocols to assist developers is a wonderful opportunity for developers and heritage stakeholders to work together to ensure that we secure our energy supplies and combat climate change, but also ensure that invaluable data generated during development supports efforts to preserve and understand this exceptional landscape. Growth in offshore development gives researchers, stakeholders and national curators the opportunity to work together to provide mitigation strategies for sustainable heritage practices that may help locate the missing evidence of human occupation of Doggerland, while also assisting green development.

Detailed mapping of Doggerland using remote sensing data has reached a point where archaeologists may begin to identify areas where accessible prehistoric land surfaces exist beneath the sea. In these areas targeted archaeological prospection may be carried out successfully. Using data provided by our industry partners, the AHRC-funded "Taken at the Flood" project will use a variety of tested and new methods to recover archaeological, environmental and sedimentological data, and provide the first evidence for in-situ, archaeological settlement in the deeper waters of the offshore zone.

The project will provide workshops and networking opportunities for academics to work

ARCHAEOLOGY ON THE CONTINENTAL SHELF

20,000 years ago, global sea-level was c. 120m lower than at present, adding 20 million km² of new territory worldwide (in red above). 3 million km² of new habitable land was added to Europe alone, of which Doggerland is the largest extent. Taken at the Flood focuses on the challenges of exploring this prehistoric landscape.

Doggerland, shown in grey in the map below, would have been an attractive place to live for Palaeolithic and Mesolithic hunter-gatherer societies. However, there is a stark contrast between the numbers of Late Palaeolithic and Mesolithic archaeological sites known

from land (yellow) and contemporary marine discoveries (red and purple). Very few finds have been recovered from offshore environments beyond territorial waters, and the majority of these are chance discoveries, which, because they were not found in situ, are of relatively limited value to archaeologists.

In comparison, the Baltic Sea, experienced very different geological stresses, leaving more shallowly submerged prehistoric landscapes closer to current coastlines, and revealing a truer reflection of in situ archaeological sites. This is partly apparent in the rich distribution of later prehistoric sites known the Store-

In 1936, the Colinda Harpoon was the only cultural evidence for prehistoric habitation in the North Sea. It was a chance find by a trawler.

*“We’re not looking for a needle, we don’t even know where the haystack is.”**

While our knowledge of the landscapes and environments of the southern North Sea have expanded with the explosion of new data, our ability to understand the people who lived in these landscapes is little more advanced today than it was to archaeologists nearly a century ago.

“the important fact, which has been sadly missed in many archaeological speculations, is that the entire coastal culture of periods I and II has been lost for the whole extent of mainland now submerged. It would be possible to take comfort from the fact that such cultures might not have existed were it not eminently probable that they not only existed, but flourished under conditions more favourable than those obtaining inland”

Grahame Clark (1936)

“for the meantime, it must be conceded that we have little more in the way of firm archaeological evidence than Clark had to hand in 1936.”

Bryony Coles (1998)

“... this terrain, thought by many to have been ‘lost’ to the seas, cannot be ignored [it was] critical to human migration and cultural diffusion. Submerged landscapes are thus essential to archaeological study around the world.”

Bynoe et al 2023

the ‘Southern River Flint’ was discovered in 2019 by targeted archaeological prospection. The first of its kind in a deep water environment.

* J.H.M. Peeters, Dagblad van het Noorden (06/05/2022)

MARINE DEVELOPMENT AND ARCHAEOLOGY

Marine development usually requires some sort of archaeological mitigation, usually undertaken by specialist contractors. In most circumstances these groups provide excellent results and this can be seen in the many reports providing information on heritage assets and obstacles including shipwrecks, aircraft, and ordnance etc.

However, the mitigation processes for prehistoric submerged archaeology are more challenging, largely as a result of a lack of knowledge of archaeological remains from these periods in marine contexts.

Windfarm development also requires the collection of very high resolution geophysical data of shallow sub-seabed strata, which may also have a high

potential for containing submerged prehistoric archaeology. This information is invaluable for archaeological purposes and provides better coverage and higher resolution mapping than is otherwise usually possible for archaeologists.

By working with industrial developers, and through our partners at Royal Haskoning DHV and Historic England, Taken at the Flood aims to utilise these data and provide new methods to identify areas that may contain these elusive archaeological deposits and provide guidance for the discovery of archaeology now and in the future.

Global Green Energy & the Law

Sources GWEC Global Wind Report 2022,
TGS Assets map

Industrial development on the continental shelf is a global phenomenon and while regional legislation or licensing developers to mitigate against damage to cultural and archaeological remains, this may not be the case in other areas of the world. A number of countries have signed the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea or ratified the UNESCO Convention on the Protection of the Underwater Cultural Heritage (shown in red, right). However, many areas impacted by development are not covered by such regulation. In these areas much of the continental shelf beyond territorial waters falls into a legislative 'jurisdictional gap', where legal protection for submerged underwater cultural heritage may be very limited.

The lack of prehistoric sites associated with marine palaeolandscapes globally indicates the need for detailed research and improved processes and guidance from the research community to support development. Taken at the Flood aims to explore new methods and processes that will aid in the discovery of such archaeological remains and provide guidance on how these processes may be employed elsewhere in the world. Without such support, continuing development of the continental shelves risks making large areas of archaeological importance inaccessible to future researchers. By working with the developers and devising new strategies to understand and investigate these landscapes, we hope to provide a new toolset useful to all parties pushing towards a net-zero solution.

In red: countries that have ratified the UNESCO Convention on the Protection of the Underwater Cultural Heritage as of 2021.

WORK TO DATE & LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

In 2023, Taken at the Flood brought together experts in the fields of archaeology, geology and chemical analysis, and partners from the energy industry to discuss what constitutes an archaeological site in a submerged context, and how we might better develop a toolkit for prospecting for submerged prehistoric archaeology.

During the workshop we focused on what we might look for, where we might

look, and what new methods could be employed to aid this investigation.

A report and paper were created from this meeting and a methodological process workflow inaugurated.

The report is available on our website at:

<https://sharpteam.at/pqwGU>

or scan the QR Code:

The Goldilocks Zone: What, Where and How?

Europe has led the way in mapping submerged palaeolandscapes. This has largely been largely on the basis of palaeoenvironmental and geomorphological research. We have yet to be able to find archaeological finds purely through targeted prospection. This is where offshore development can help.

The same shallow geophysical data that advises our industry partners on potential hazards in site location can be employed to identify likely targets with high archaeological potential. This will allow us to designate areas of potential priority for further investigation, or potential risk, and equally identify areas where 'in situ' archaeology is less likely to be found. Locations of priority would be those deemed to meet all three of the characteristics outlined by the 'Goldilocks Zone':

- 1) The potential for human activity, based on our knowledge of terrestrial archaeology
- 2) Environmental conditions conducive to the preservation of archaeology, and with minimal exposure to subsequent disruption.
- 3) An accessible location for potential investigative methods, eg. vibrocoring may access a sub seafloor depth of 5m while a dredge is limited to surface outcrop.

Archaeologists can seek out such locations using data provided by Taken at the Flood partners Royal Haskoning DHV, supported by Historic England. These are already providing new areas to focus research in pursuit of the marine Goldilocks Zone. Currently, the project has targeted two areas of the southern North Sea where windfarms are either currently being developed, or will be soon, and which have also been sources of previous chance archaeological finds. These are the Brown Banks and a submarine channel known as the Southern River. Archaeological finds have been made in these areas, but no in situ findspots have yet been located. In 2024, these survey targets will be tested to see if the provenance of archaeological remains in these areas can be securely located.

The two areas of focus for 2024 ship missions are marked in red above. The Southern River is a distinct palaeo-feature located just beyond the 12nm UK territorial water. The Brown Banks lie across the territorial line in Dutch waters. The above map also shows the locations of known chance finds.

Above: Chance finds thought to be from eroding peats. Below: Proposed extent of Holocene peat bed in the Brown Bank area.

The Brown Banks

Recent surveying and coring has allowed us to create extensive and detailed maps of a submerged archaeological landscape in the area of the Brown Banks (Missiaen et al 2021). The varied topography of this area was likely an important area for prehistoric people, and proxies of human activity have been found for decades in the form of unstratified bones and artefacts dredged by fishing vessels, yet to date it has not been possible to ascertain precisely from where these finds came from.

Taken at the Flood has identified a wide, partially eroded river channel, with a Holocene land surface to either side. This is mostly comprised of a contiguous peat bed, outcropping in parts of the current sea-bed.

We will visit this area in 2024 to perform a tight grid-survey of focused areas, coring the peat edges, and attempting to locate archaeological artefacts employing a gilson dredge and Harmon grabs. We aim to also use a robotic autonomous vehicle to give us visibility of the peat beds.

The Southern River

The Southern River area has many points of archaeological interest.

- Core evidence reveals a potential freshwater spring near a saddle fen peat deposit.
- Simulations have suggested the mouth of the river was relatively static for long periods during sea-level rise.
- Hammerstone debitage was discovered in the river mouth, via a dredge. The famous Colinda Point was discovered less than 30km from this river channel (Gaffney and Fitch 2022).

Interpreted palaeo-environmental map showing the Southern River. Note the Colinda Point and hammerstone locations are nearby

Work With Us FOR A GREENER FUTURE

Taken at the Flood is working to promote best practice in offshore archaeological prospection and the management of marine cultural heritage. The project will work with the offshore industry to produce guidance, and to support development on the continental shelf. The project looks to the future while respecting the past. To achieve this, the project wants to engage with industry partners, and benefit from expertise and knowledge. If you can assist in preserving the prehistoric heritage of the southern North Sea, we would really like to hear from you. Please contact us by email at submergedlandscapes@bradford.ac.uk or via our website, which you can access by scanning the QR Code below.

Chris Pater
Historic England

Vic Boothby & Claire Mellet
Royal Haskoning, DHV

Tine Missiaen & Ruth Plets
Flanders Marine Institute, VLIZ

Vincent Gaffney, Andy Fraser & James Walker
University of Bradford

Citations and Credits

Amkreutz and van der Vaart-Verschoof (ed.) 2022. *Doggerland. Lost World under the North Sea* Sidestone Press, Leiden. 209 ISBN: 9789464261134

Bynoe R., Benjamin J. and N.C. Flemming 2023. *Archaeology of the Continental Shelf: Submerged Cultural Landscapes* In A. S. Gilbert et al. (eds.), *Encyclopaedia of Geoarchaeology*. London, Springer. 1-25.

GWEC Global Wind Report 2022 Global Wind Energy Council. (<https://gwec.net/global-wind-report-2022/>),

Clark, J.G.D. 1936. *The Mesolithic Settlement of Northern Europe. A study of the food-gathering peoples of Northern Europe during the early post-glacial period*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Coles, B.J. 1998. *Doggerland: a speculative survey*. *Proceedings of the Prehistoric Society* 64: 45-81.

Evans A. M. and M.E. Keith 2019. *Submerged Prehistoric Archaeology: Confronting Issues of Scale and Context on the Gulf of Mexico Outer Continental Shelf* (Offshore Technology Conference <https://onepetro.org/OTCONF/proceedings-abstract/19OTC/1-19OTC/181530>)

Fitch, S., Gaffney, V., Harding, R., Walker, J., Bates, C.R., Bates, M. and Fraser, A., 2022. *A description of palaeolandscape features in the southern North Sea*. *Europe's Lost frontiers*. Vol. 1 Context and Methodology. Ed Gaffney, V., Fitch, S. Archaeopress.

Missiaen, T., Fitch, S., Harding, R., Muru, M., Fraser, A., De Clercq, M., Moreno, D.G., Versteeg, W., Busschers, F.S., van Heteren, S. and Hijma, M.P., 2021. *Targeting the Mesolithic: Interdisciplinary approaches to archaeological prospection in the Brown Bank area, southern North Sea*. *Quaternary International*, 584, pp.141-151.

TGS Assets Map TGS/4COffshore (2023) Wind Pathfinder (<https://wind.tgs.ai/>)

Images courtesy of Dr Anders Fischer

SUBMERGED LANDSCAPES CENTRE

Arts and
Humanities
Research Council

UNIVERSITY of
BRADFORD

Historic England

Royal
HaskoningDHV
Enhancing Society Together

Prifysgol Cymru
Y Drindod Dewi Sant
University of Wales
Trinity Saint David

WARWICK

X-RAY
MINERAL SERVICES
UK

Contact: submergedlandscapes@bradford.ac.uk